

Supplementary Material: Formal Proofs and Analytical Subsumption for CLASS

Accompanying "CLASS: A Constrained Linear Algebraic Search for SAT-to-Ising Transformations"

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Abstract. This document provides formal mathematical derivations supporting the CLASS framework. Section 1 proves the algebraic necessity of auxiliary variables for encoding 3-SAT clauses. Section 2 provides a step-by-step constructive proof showing that historical mapping families are specific, normalized subsets of the CLASS search space.

1 Formal Proof: Necessity of Auxiliary Variables for 3-SAT Mappings

We provide a formal algebraic proof demonstrating that a 3-SAT clause cannot be mapped to a standard Ising Hamiltonian using only three spins. Such a system is fundamentally over-constrained and inconsistent without auxiliary degrees of freedom.

Consider a standard 3-SAT clause: $(x_1 \vee x_2 \vee x_3)$. We map each literal to an independent Ising spin $s_i \in \{-1, +1\}$. Let the spin vector be $\mathbf{s} = [s_1, s_2, s_3]^\top$ and the parameter vector comprising local biases and pairwise couplings be $\mathbf{c} = [c_1, c_2, c_3, c_{12}, c_{13}, c_{23}]^\top$. The Hamiltonian is:

$$H(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{c}) = \sum_{i=1}^3 c_i s_i + \sum_{i < j} c_{ij} s_i s_j \quad (1)$$

For functional equivalence, the single unsatisfying assignment $([-1, -1, -1]^\top)$ must yield an energy strictly greater than the global minimum H_{\min} , while the seven satisfying assignments must evaluate exactly to H_{\min} . This requires:

$$H([-1, -1, -1]^\top, \mathbf{c}) > H_{\min} \quad (2)$$

and for the seven satisfying configurations $\{\mathbf{s}_1, \dots, \mathbf{s}_7\}$:

$$H(\mathbf{s}_k, \mathbf{c}) = H_{\min}, \quad \forall k \in \{1, \dots, 7\} \quad (3)$$

The equality constraints in (3) form a matrix equation $A\mathbf{c} = \mathbf{b}$, where $A \in \mathbb{R}^{7 \times 6}$. Each of the seven rows in A corresponds to one of the satisfying spin configurations

$\mathbf{s}_k = [s_1, s_2, s_3]^\top$. The columns evaluate the corresponding linear and quadratic terms $[s_1, s_2, s_3, s_1s_2, s_1s_3, s_2s_3]$ for that specific state:

$$\underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} -1 & -1 & 1 & 1 & -1 & -1 \\ -1 & 1 & -1 & -1 & 1 & -1 \\ -1 & 1 & 1 & -1 & -1 & 1 \\ 1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & 1 \\ 1 & -1 & 1 & -1 & 1 & -1 \\ 1 & 1 & -1 & 1 & -1 & -1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}}_A \cdot \mathbf{c} = H_{\min} \mathbf{1}_7$$

This system comprises seven linear equations with six unknowns. For a valid solution to exist, the rank of the coefficient matrix A must equal the rank of the augmented matrix $[A \mid \mathbf{b}]$. Evaluation reveals:

$$\text{rank}(A) = 6, \quad \text{whereas} \quad \text{rank}([A \mid H_{\min} \mathbf{1}_7]) = 7$$

Since $\text{rank}([A \mid \mathbf{b}]) > \text{rank}(A)$, the system is fundamentally inconsistent. No real-valued coefficient vector $\mathbf{c} \in \mathbb{R}^6$ can satisfy all constraints simultaneously.

Conclusion: An Ising Hamiltonian restricted to three spins cannot encode a 3-SAT clause. An auxiliary spin is required to expand the parameter space and provide the degrees of freedom necessary to resolve this algebraic inconsistency.

2 Proving Analytical Equivalence: The Chancellor Mapping and CLASS Subspaces

In this section, we demonstrate the exact mathematical equivalence between the two valid operational branches of the Chancellor formulation and the explicitly derived CLASS subspaces **C1** and **C6**. By normalizing their respective energy landscapes to a uniform ground state, we prove that Chancellor’s ad-hoc configurations are simply alternate parameterizations of these two canonical continuous spaces.

2.1 Analytical Derivation of the CLASS Subspaces

The CLASS framework identifies families of valid SAT-to-Ising mappings by solving a system of linear constraints that enforce logical correctness over the energy landscape. For a 3-SAT clause with one auxiliary spin, the coefficient vector \mathbf{c} consists of ten parameters:

$$\mathbf{c} = [c_1, c_2, c_3, c_{12}, c_{13}, c_{23}, c_{\text{aux}}, c_{1a}, c_{2a}, c_{3a}]^\top. \quad (4)$$

Subspace C1 (Literal Symmetry) Imposing symmetry across literals ($c_1 = c_2 = c_3$) reduces the system to a one-parameter family governed by k_2 :

$$\begin{aligned} c_1, c_2, c_3 &= k_2 \\ c_{12}, c_{13}, c_{23} &= -1 - 3k_2 \\ c_{\text{aux}} &= 2 + 3k_2 \\ c_{1a}, c_{2a}, c_{3a} &= k_2 \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Subspace C6 (Coupling Symmetry) Alternatively, enforcing symmetry across pairwise couplings ($c_{12} = c_{13} = c_{23}$) yields:

$$\begin{aligned} c_1, c_2, c_3 &= 1 - 3k_2 \\ c_{12}, c_{13}, c_{23} &= k_2 \\ c_{\text{aux}} &= -1 + 3k_2 \\ c_{1a}, c_{2a}, c_{3a} &= k_2 - 1 \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

2.2 The Chancellor Formulation and its Valid Branches

The general mapping proposed by Chancellor [1] parameterizes the Ising coefficients using a logical bias h and a coupling strength $J > |h|$:

$$\mathbf{c}_{\text{Chan}} = [h - 1, h - 1, h - 1, J + 1, J + 1, J + 1, 2h, 2J, 2J, 2J]^\top. \quad (7)$$

To ensure this configuration yields a valid, uniformly degenerate mapping, the parameters must restrict to one of two specific operational branches:

Branch A: Defined by $h = -1$. Substituting this yields the unnormalized coefficient vector, which exhibits a ground-state energy of $E_{\min} = -(3J + 1)$:

$$\mathbf{c}_{\text{ChanA}} = [-2, -2, -2, J + 1, J + 1, J + 1, -2, 2J, 2J, 2J]^\top. \quad (8)$$

Branch B: Defined by $h = 1 - 2J$. This yields a distinct unnormalized vector with a ground-state energy of $E_{\min} = -(5J - 1)$:

$$\mathbf{c}_{\text{ChanB}} = [-2J, -2J, -2J, J + 1, J + 1, J + 1, 2 - 4J, 2J, 2J, 2J]^\top. \quad (9)$$

2.3 Proving Equivalence to CLASS Subspaces

To rigorously compare the Chancellor branches to the CLASS subspaces, we must normalize the unnormalized Chancellor vectors to match the CLASS uniform ground state convention of $H_{\min} = -1$. This is achieved by dividing each branch by its respective absolute ground-state energy, $-E_{\min}$.

Equivalence: Branch A \equiv Subspace C1 Scaling $\mathbf{c}_{\text{ChanA}}$ by its ground-state energy $(3J + 1)$ yields the normalized vector:

$$\hat{\mathbf{c}}_{\text{ChanA}} = \frac{1}{3J + 1} [-2, -2, -2, J + 1, J + 1, J + 1, -2, 2J, 2J, 2J]^\top. \quad (10)$$

Equating the literal bias component \hat{c}_1 of this normalized vector to the Subspace **C1** parameter ($c_1 = k_2$) defines the necessary coordinate transformation:

$$k_2 = \frac{-2}{3J + 1}. \quad (11)$$

Substituting this specific k_2 mapping into the general **C1** basis (Equation (5)) exactly recovers all ten coefficients of the $\hat{\mathbf{c}}_{\text{ChanA}}$ vector. This proves that Chancellor Branch A is an alternate parameterization of the **C1** subspace.

Equivalence: Branch B \equiv Subspace C6 Similarly, scaling $\mathbf{c}_{\text{ChanB}}$ by its ground-state energy $(5J - 1)$ provides the normalized vector:

$$\hat{\mathbf{c}}_{\text{ChanB}} = \frac{1}{5J - 1} [-2J, -2J, -2J, J + 1, J + 1, J + 1, 2 - 4J, 2J, 2J, 2J]^\top. \quad (12)$$

Equating the internal coupling component \hat{c}_{12} of this normalized vector to the Subspace **C6** parameter ($c_{12} = k_2$) yields the transformation:

$$k_2 = \frac{J + 1}{5J - 1}. \quad (13)$$

Substituting this k_2 mapping into the general **C6** basis (Equation (6)) perfectly recovers the full $\hat{\mathbf{c}}_{\text{ChanB}}$ vector, proving that Chancellor Branch B is equivalent to the **C6** subspace.

2.4 Linearity and Analytical Tractability

This mathematical correspondence highlights a crucial structural distinction. In the original Chancellor parameterization, the mapping energies depend on J as rational functions (e.g., $\frac{aJ+b}{cJ+d}$). This non-linear formulation introduces asymptotic behavior, making it difficult to algebraically identify optimal coordinates and strict operational boundaries.

Conversely, the CLASS framework defines all energy levels as strictly linear functions of a single parameter ($H = mk_2 + b$). This linearity makes calculating intersection boundaries, tracking level crossings, and analytically maximizing the Hamiltonian gap a straightforward and transparent algebraic exercise.

References

1. N. Chancellor, S. Zohren, P.A. Warburton, S.C. Benjamin, S. and Roberts: A direct mapping of max k-SAT and high order parity checks to a Chimera graph. *Scientific Reports* **6**, 37107 (2016)